

INTRODUCTION

Current joining methods are labour-intensive, require extensive surface preparation or fastener holes that create stress concentrations and break fibre continuity [1].

Requirements for **novel joining methods** [2,3]:

- (i) applicable for thermoset & thermoplastic composites
- (ii) improve structural efficiency
- (iii) ease repair and disassembly
- (iv) meet certification requirements

Fusion bonding thermoset composites

- **Thermoplastic-rich surface layer** required [2]
- Performance study of **Mode I fracture toughness**
- Influence of key processing parameters studied using **Gaussian Process modelling**

METHODOLOGY

Materials & manufacturing

Thermoset laminates:

Co-bonded HexPly® IM7/8552 (CF/epoxy) & polyetherimide (PEI) film (grade ULTEM 1000) PEI film forms a **weldable surface layer** (coupling layer)

Heating element (placed at the joint interface):

Stainless steel mesh conductor & 2 plies of Toray TC1000/EC5 (GF/PEI)

Figure 1: Illustration of a resistance-welded CF/epoxy joint.

Resistance welding was performed using an in-house developed 10 kW welding rig. 3 main processing parameters studied: (i) **temperature**, (ii) **pressure** & (iii) **constant time**

Table 1: Studied welding parameter ranges.

Parameter	Minimum	Maximum
Temperature [°C]	250	350
Time [s]	10	90
Pressure [MPa]	0.7	1.5

Fracture toughness analysis & Gaussian Process modelling

Processing parameters influence on joint performance assessed via:

- **Double cantilever beam tests** according to ASTM D5528 - **Mode I fracture toughness**
- 15 different parameter combinations

Gaussian Process defined via: mean $\mu(x)$ & covariance $k(x, x')$ functions.

Given training points (X, f) and yet unobserved data points (X^*, f^*) , the posterior distribution is

$$\begin{bmatrix} f \\ f^* \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mu_X \\ \mu_{X^*} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} K_{X,X} & K_{X,X^*} \\ K_{X^*,X} & K_{X^*,X^*} \end{bmatrix} \right).$$

$K_{i,j}$ is a submatrix, whereby each element is defined by a kernel function and is given by

$$K_{i,j} = A \exp \left(\frac{-\|x_i - x_j\|^2}{2l^2} \right) + K_{noise}, \text{ where } K_{noise} = \lambda, \text{ if } x_i \equiv x_j, \text{ else } 0.$$

RESULTS

Load vs. cross-head displacement and Mode I toughness values vs. crack extension are shown for a high- and a poor performance weld in Figure 2.a and 2.b, and Figure 2.c and 2.d respectively.

Figure 2: Comparison of load vs. crosshead displacement curves and R-curves shown for a high- in (a) and (b), and in (c) and (d) for a weak performing joint respectively.

Mode I performance of resistance-welded CF/epoxy

- **Comparable fracture toughness to pristine CF/PEI laminate**
- **Significant fracture toughness improvement** compared to **thermoset adhesive bonding**
- **No need for complex surface preparation**
- Assembly **cycle times up to 98 % shorter** than for thermoset adhesively bonded joints

Fracture behaviour & joint fractography

- Primarily **cohesive failure** mode with local fibre-bridging between coupling layers & GF/PEI plies
- **Insufficiently processed** joints show poor polymer interdiffusion (**reprocessable**)
- **Overprocessed** joints showed **thermal degradation** of the thermoset matrix

Figure 3: Fracture surface micrograph of a (a) good quality, (b) insufficiently processed and (c) overprocessed welded joint.

Processing windows using Gaussian Processes

- 3-dimensional **multivariate Gaussian Process** model trained with empirical data
- Predict the Mode I fracture toughness & identify the correlation between key processing parameters

Figure 4: GP model posterior prediction of Mode I fracture toughness with respect to temperature & pressure at increasing constant welding times (a) 20 s, (b) 40 s, (c) 60 s and (d) 80 s.

- **Wide range of processing parameters** yields **high-performance** joints
- Lower temperatures: higher pressure & longer processing time (reduced risk of overprocessing)
- Higher temperatures: lower pressures & short welding times

Recommended processing parameters, based on lower bound 95 % confidence interval of the posterior prediction, are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2: Recommended welding parameter ranges yielding high-performance joints.

Parameter	Minimum	Maximum
Temperature [°C]	300	325
Time [s]	30	55
Pressure [MPa]	0.85	1.0

CONCLUSION

- **Resistance welding** is a highly promising new method for **joining thermoset composites**
- Fracture toughness is comparable to high-performance aerospace grade thermoplastic composites
- **Radical fracture toughness improvement** when compared to thermoset adhesively bonded joints
- **Gaussian Process** modelling successfully used to **predict optimum processing windows**
- Influence of processing parameters on the joint's performance was studied

Future work will focus on rigorous testing to demonstrate process robustness & repeatability and investigate additional mechanical properties of the joint.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Xie, H. Liu, W. Wu, D. Abliz, Y. Duan and D. Li, Fusion bonding of thermosets composite structures with thermoplastic binder co-cure and prepreg interlayer in electrical resistance welding, *Materials and Design*, **98**, May 2016, pp. 143-149.
- [2] C. Brauner, S. Nakouzi, L. Zweifel and J. Tresch, Co-curing behaviour of thermoset composites with a thermoplastic boundary layer for welding purposes, *Adv. Compos. Lett.*, **29**, Mar. 2020, pp. 1-9.
- [3] X. Xiong, D. Wang, J. Wei, P. Zhao, R. Ren, J. Dong and X. Cui, Resistance welding technology of fiber reinforced polymer composites: a review, *J. Adhes. Sci. Technol.*, **35(15)**, Jan. 2021, pp. 1593-1619.

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